

A 0.3 THz Transmitter in 90-nm BiCMOS Technology for Energy-Efficient High Data Rate Communication

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Abstract—In this work, an energy-efficiency high data rate transmitter at 0.3 THz is presented. The design is implemented in Infineon’s 90-nm SiGe BiCMOS technology. The 3-dB RF bandwidth is between 254–303 GHz, and the 3-dB IF bandwidth is 32 GHz. The transmitter is evaluated to support OOK data rates up to 32 Gbps, and 40 Gbps QPSK using an IF carrier. The DC power consumption is 285 mW.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand of high data rate communication is growing rapidly. To increase the data rate, one can increase the bandwidth or increase the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [1]. Millimeter wave frequencies offer wide available bandwidth, but it is challenging to achieve high output power. In an Indium phosphide (InP) HBT technology, a 0.3 THz transmitter achieved 20 Gbps [2]. Here, we investigate the potential of using a silicon germanium (SiGe) process to design a 0.3 THz transmitter. The H-band transmitter is designed and manufactured a 90-nm SiGe BiCMOS process (B12HFC) developed by Infineon technologies. The process includes high-speed npn HBTs with f_t/f_{max} of 300 GHz/500 GHz [3]. The transmitter (Fig. 1) consists of a times eight LO frequency multiplier and a balanced up converter.

Fig. 1. A block diagram of the transmitter.

The schematic of the transmitter (Fig. 2), shows two cascaded frequency doublers using the same class B biased differential pair topology. The buffer amplifier (D-band) is a two-stage common emitter configuration. The last stage doubler does not have the cascoded transistor, due to limited gain at high frequencies. Finally, the mixer core is a balanced Gilbert cell.

The layout (Fig. 3) uses many folded Marchand baluns, to convert single-ended to differential, because of their broadband performance.

II. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

For the frequency domain measurements, a Keysight PNA-X (67 GHz N5247A) was used together with a VDI H-band extender WR 3.4 at the output. For a balanced IF input, an external balun (Marki BAL-0050) was used. The conversion gain for the transmitter was measured first by sweeping the RF frequency (Fig. 4), then the IF frequency was swept (Fig. 5).

Fig. 2. A simplified schematic of the 300 GHz transmitter.

Fig. 3. A photo of the fabricated transmitter. The size of the transmitter is 1590 μm by 630 μm .

Fig. 4. Measured conversion gain for the transmitter sweeping the RF frequency. The IF frequency was 1 GHz.

Fig. 5. Measured conversion gain of the transmitter sweeping the IF signal.

The setup (Fig. 6) used during the transmission test, where the carrier was set to 300 GHz. Data input was provided by a Keysight M8195A arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), which generated a pseudorandom binary sequence (PRBS-11) using root-raised cosine pulse shaping with a roll-off of 0.8. Furthermore, direct conversion was used in the first part of the evaluation. The transmitted signal was captured through a probe that was connected to a WR 3.4 VDI Compact Converter (CC). The down converted single-ended output signal from the CC was then connected to a Keysight UXR1104A Infiniium Real-Time Oscilloscope for evaluation. The error vector magnitude (EVM), and SNR were measured.

Fig. 6. The measurement setup that was used during the time domain measurements.

The received eye diagram of a 25 Gbps (Fig. 7), and a 32 Gbps (Fig. 8) on-off-keying (OOK) transmission.

Fig. 7. Received eye diagram of a demodulated 25 Gbps OOK transmission. EVM=9.9% and SNR=20.1 dB.

Fig. 8. Received eye diagram of a demodulated 32 Gbps OOK transmission. EVM=11.8% and SNR=18.6 dB.

Moreover, the transmitter was also evaluated using an IF carrier to achieve quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) modulation transmissions. Symbol rates between 10 and 20 GBd were used corresponding to 20 to 40 Gbps. The received constellations can be seen in Fig. 9, Fig. 10, and Fig. 11.

The IF carrier used for the 10 GBd transmission was 9 GHz, and 16 GHz was used for the 15 and 20 GBd transmissions.

Fig. 9. Received I/Q constellation for a 10 GBd QPSK transmission. EVM=13.2% and SNR=17.6 dB.

Fig. 10. Received I/Q constellation for a 15 GBd QPSK transmission. EVM=19.7% and SNR=14.1 dB.

Fig. 11. Received I/Q constellation for a 20 GBd QPSK transmission. EVM=25.4% and SNR=11.9 dB.

The DC power consumption for the transmitter is 285 mW, resulting in a 7.1 pJ/bit energy efficiency for the 40 Gbps transmission.

III. CONCLUSION

This work presents an energy-efficient H-band transmitter in a SiGe BiCMOS technology. The transmitter has a 49 GHz 3-dB RF bandwidth and a 32 GHz 3-dB IF bandwidth. It supports direct modulated OOK data rates of 32 Gbps, and 40 Gbps using an IF carrier. These results demonstrate the potential of high frequency/data rate transmitters using this technology.

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